

DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIORENAL SYNDROME IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

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Introduction: Arterial hypertension (AH) is one of the most common diseases. It is a major risk factor for myocardial infarction, acute cerebral circulatory failure, heart failure and mortality.

Purpose: To evaluate the features of cardiorenal syndrome in women with arterial hypertension.

Material and Methods: A study of 65 women (mean age 52 years) with AH was conducted. Patients were divided into 2 groups according to body mass index (BMI). Group 1 consisted of 30 patients with AH and BMI up to 27 kg/m², group 2 - 35 patients with AH and obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m², volume to waist ratio >0.8). All patients underwent general chemical methods of examination. daily monitoring of blood pressure (BP), ECHO CG, renal functional status by determination of creatinine, glomerular filtration rate (GFR) according to MDRD equation, daily urinary excretion of albumin (MAU).

Results: Differences in blood pressure variability (BPV), time index (TI) were revealed in all examined patients. The level of VAD increased significantly in both groups, but in group 2 of obese women it was 1.5 times higher, and the TI increased more during the night time 1.8 times in group 1 and 2.5 times in group 2. Diastolic dysfunction of the left ventricle, increased left ventricular myocardial mass index (LVMI) by 1.5 times and 1.6 times, respectively. Concentric LV hypertrophy was detected in 44.2% of group1 patients and 55.8% of obese AH women, eccentric LV hypertrophy in 10.3% and 12.1% of patients, respectively. Mean serum creatinine values did not differ significantly between them, but the percentage of patients with elevated creatinine was higher in group2 (2.8% and 9.7%, respectively). In parallel, in obese AH patients, the number of patients with SCF < 70 ml/min/1.73m³ increased from 4.0% in group 1 to 10.4% in group 2, with an increase in glomerular filtration from 87.3 ml/min/1.73m² to 97.2 ml/min/1.73m², which is probably due to increased renal blood flow. A high percentage of MAU was found in women with AH. Thus, it was 27.2% in obese patients and 11.0% in non-obese women; the level of daily albumin increased in group 1 to 46.84 mg/l and in group 2 to 61.23 mg/l. Increased MAU in women becomes a predictor of arterial hypertension with the development of renal failure, which is more significant in the presence of obesity and is a marker of early renal vascular dysfunction with the subsequent

development of chronic kidney disease. Correlation analysis of the magnitude and rate of morning rise of CAD and DA in women with AH revealed a correlation between IV DA and MAU, reflecting the state of intraclubular haemodynamics. With the development of obesity, a correlation between the functional state of the kidneys and the diastolic function of the heart was found.

Conclusion: Thus, in women with AH, careful investigation of the structural and functional status of the kidneys should be performed, especially in the presence of obesity.

